

Migration Diaspora And Remittance Review

Volume: 4
Issue: 1
Year: 2024
ISSN: 2791-254X

Local Entrepreneurship Enhancing Socioeconomic Status: A Case Study on Performance and Impact of National Minorities Development & Finance Corporation (NMDFC) Scheme in Kohima District of Nagaland

Miss Nchumbeni S Ovung¹
Dr Debojit Konwar²

¹Research Scholar, St. Joseph University Nagaland, India

²Associate Professor, St. Joseph University Nagaland, India

Corresponding Author: Miss Nchumbeni S Ovung

Email: nchumabci@gmail.com

Abstract

The National Minorities Development & Finance Corporation (NMDFC) has various types of loans but in Nagaland microfinance was initiated on 30th September 1994 and was targeted only to women and Self Help Groups (SHG's). Under the scheme, an amount of Rs. 1 lakhs under credit Line-1 & up to Rs. 1.5 lakhs under Credit Line-2 is extended to each member of SHGs at interest rates of 7% & 10% respectively. A concession of 2% is extended to women beneficiaries under Credit Line-2. The study is based on primary sources and has attempted to highlight the impact of schemes with and without support and the performance of NMDFC in productivity, reduction of cost, and introduction of input in the state.

Keywords

National Minorities Development & Finance Corporation (NMDFC), State Channelizing Agencies (SCAs), Self Help Groups (SHG's), Micro Finance, Women Beneficiaries

Introduction

National Minorities Development & Finance Corporation (NMDFC) is a Govt. The company is under section 8 of the Companies Act 2013, under the administrative control of the Ministry of Minority Affairs, Government of India. The Corporation has been set up to promote economic development for the benefit of "Backward Sections" amongst

Migration Diaspora and Remittance Review

453-461

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Licensee KMF Publishers (www.kmf-publishers.com). This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Article reuse guidelines:

Open Access

<http://kmf-publishers.com/mdrr/>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.>

the Minority Communities i.e. Muslims, Christians, Sikhs, Buddhists, Parsis & Jains, with preference being given to the occupational group and women. NMDFC implements its schemes & programs through State Channelizing Agencies (SCAs) nominated by the respective State Governments & Banking Partners.

Based on annual income, the target group is bifurcated into two credit lines as follows:

- Credit Line-1, the benefits are available for persons having annual family income up to Rs.98, 000/- in rural areas and up to Rs.1.20 lakhs in urban areas.
- Credit Line-2, the benefits are available to persons with an annual family income of up to Rs. 8.00 lacs.

Micro-Finance Scheme: Under this Scheme, credit is extended to the members of the Self-Help Groups (SHGs), predominantly comprising of minority women scattered in remote villages and urban slums, who are not able to take advantage of the formal banking credit. Under the scheme, an amount of Rs. 1 lakh under credit Line-1 & up to Rs. 1.5 lacs under Credit Line-2 is extended to each member of SHG at an interest rate of 7% & 10% respectively. A concession of 2% is extended to women beneficiaries under Credit Line-2.

Objectives

- To study the impact of the schemes with and without NMDFC loans in Kohima Districts
- To study the performance of NMDFC in Kohima districts.

Hypothesis

HO= The Government Support boosts productivity and generates employment

Methodology

The study is empirical and based on primary data and the secondary data is taken from different articles, the internet, and annual reports. A multistage stratified random sampling technique has been used and a total of 150 samples were taken from Kohima districts out of which only 9 beneficiaries were recorded for the study. Those respondents who took government support invested in setting up thrift shops, graphic designing shops, expanding clinic and grocery shops and gift shops, etc.

Limitations

- The primary data is for the period of 2021-22.
- Only one district was taken for the study out of 16 districts in Nagaland.
- The study relates to the expressed opinion of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

Multinomial Logistic Regression and paired 't' test (in case of two dependent or correlated of equal two samples) have been used for the analysis. Monetary value is the dependent variable and the independent variables are age, occupation, education, and knowledge of NMDFC.

Table 1: Case Processing Summary without NMDFC Loan

		N	Marginal Percentage
Income	Below 3000	85	56.7%
	3000-10000	40	26.7%
	15000-20000	5	3.3%
	20000 & above	20	13.3%
Age	Below 20	1	.7%
	20-30 yrs	27	18.0%
	30-40 yrs	56	37.3%
	40-50 yrs	34	22.7%
	50 & above	32	21.3%
Occupation	Farmer	102	68.0%
	Govt. Service	22	14.7%
	Self employed	18	12.0%
	Others	8	5.3%
Education	Illiterate	1	.7%
	Primary	83	55.3%
	Secondary	20	13.3%
	Higher secondary	15	10.0%
	Graduate and above	31	20.7%
Knowledge	Yes	18	12.0%
	No	132	88.0%
Valid	150	100.0%	
Missing	0		
Total	150		
Subpopulation	46 ^a		

Table 2: Likelihood Ratio Test

Effect	Model	Fitting		
	Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept	66.900 ^a	.000	0	.
Age	78.665	11.765	12	.465
Occupation	1.738E2 ^b	106.898	9	.000
Education	77.156 ^b	10.256	12	.593
Knowledge	68.818 ^b	1.918	3	.590

The above table 1 and 2 show the results of the respondents without NMDFC support. The likelihood ratio test proves that the independent or predictor variables such as occupation ($p=0.00<0.05$) are significant and the other independent variables such as age ($p=0.465>0.05$), education ($p=0.593 >0.05$) and knowledge of NMDFC ($p=0.590 >0.05$) are not significant as their p values are higher than 0.05.

Table 3: Case Processing Summary with NMDFC Loan

Effect	Model	Fitting		
	Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept	66.900 ^a	.000	0	.
Age	78.665	11.765	12	.465
Occupation	1.738E2 ^b	106.898	9	.000
Education	77.156 ^b	10.256	12	.593
Knowledge	68.818 ^b	1.918	3	.590

Table 4: Likelihood Ratio Test

Effect	Model	Fitting			
	Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests			
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Intercept	67.746 ^a	.000	0	.	
Age	79.937 ^b	12.191	12	.430	
Occupation	168.412	100.666	9	.000	
Education	84.639 ^b	16.893	12	.154	
Knowledge	75.887 ^b	8.141	3	.043	

The above table 3 and 4 show the results of the respondents with NMDFC support. The likelihood ratio test proves that the independent or predictor variables such as occupation ($p=0.00<0.05$) and knowledge of NMDFC ($p=0.590<0.05$) are significant while the other independent variables such as age ($p=0.430>0.05$) and education ($p=0.154 >0.05$) are not significant as their p values are higher than 0.05.

We can conclude that the respondents with NMDFC support have better results than those without NMDFC and that it is important to know about the schemes to avail and make use of it by setting up various businesses, expanding the existing business, etc.

Impact of MNDFC Scheme on Productivity

Table 5.1: Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Part 1 Before	20444.4444	9	12521.09331	4173.69777
After	30555.5556	9	18276.42683	6092.14228

Table 5.2: Paired Samples Correlation

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Part 1 Before & After	9	.979	.000

Table 5.3: Paired Sample test

		Paired Differences					Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	t	
					Lower	Upper	
Part 1 Before & After	-	10111.1111	6527.71868	2175.90623	-15128.75986	5093.46236	4.6487

From the above Table 5 (1, 2 &3), the value in Kohima district is found to be -4.647 and the p-value is 0.002, which is less than 0.05 ($p=0.002<0.05$). Therefore, we can say that government support boosts the productivity of the respondents

Paired T-Test of Change in Reduction of Cost

Table 6.1: Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Part 1 Before	9388.8889	9	7423.68582	2474.56194
After	6066.6667	9	5676.92699	1892.30900

Table 6.2: Paired Samples Correlation

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Part 1 Before & After	9	.922	.000

Table 6.3: Paired Sample test

		Paired Differences							
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
					Lower	Upper			
Part 1		3322.222	3101.925	1033.975	937.8708	5706.573	3.2		
Before & After	22	93	31	9	56	13	8	.01	

From the above table 6 (1, 2 &3), the ‘t’ value in Kohima district is found to be 3.213 and the p-value is 0.01, which is less than 0.01 ($p=0.01 < 0.05$). Therefore, we can say that with government support the entrepreneurs reduce their cost of production.

Paired T-Test of Change in Introduction of Inputs

The input introduction includes labour employment, machinery tools, and the use of fertilizers and pesticides.

Table 7.1: Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Part 1 Before	3644.4444	9	4802.37210	1600.79070
After	7555.5556	9	9322.16594	3107.38865

Table 7.2: Paired Samples Correlation

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Part 1 Before & After	9	.998	.000

Table 7.3: Paired Sample test

		Paired Differences					Sig.			
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Interval of the Difference	Lower	Upper	t	df	tail
Part 1	-	3911.111	4535.5386	1511.8462	7397.434	424.7874	2.58	8	.03	
Before & After	11				76	6	7			

From the above table 7 (1, 2 &3), the ‘t’ value in Kohima district is found to be -2.587 and the p-value is 0.03, which is less than 0.05 ($p=0.03<0.05$). Therefore, we can say that with government support there is an increase in labour employment, introduction to machinery tools, and use of fertilizers and pesticides.

For the hypothesis, we can conclude that government schemes boost productivity and generate employment

Conclusion

The study is based on observation and primary sources might have some limitations. The study shows that only 6 percent of the respondents seek government support i.e. NMDFC scheme. Knowledge plays an important role in the NMDFC scheme as with proper knowledge they can avail of the scheme and utilize it efficiently; only 12 percent knew about the scheme and 88 percent did not know. With the support of government schemes there is an increase in productivity, reduce in the cost of production, and an increase in input introduction such as labour employment, machinery tools, and use of fertilizers as the paired sample statistics the probability value ($P<0.05$) which indicates the scheme has a positive impact in production, reduction of cost, productivity, etc.

The scheme can have a better performance if certain initiatives are taken to reach out to women and SHG’s in Nagaland. More awareness programme and advertising should be conducted for better knowledge about the scheme in rural areas.

References

Bhagyalaxmi M and Dr Ishwara P (2014): Dual Responsibility of Rural Women Entrepreneurs- Issues and Challenges, GJRA Global Journal For Research Analysis Vol. 3 (7).

- Elena Bardasi, Shwetlena Sabarwal, Katherine Terrell (2011), How do Female Entrepreneurs Perform? Evidence from Three Developing Regions, Springer Small Bus Econ, Vol. 37(4), pp 417-441.
- Anjali Kaushik, Amit Kumar Gupta & Niva Bhandari, (2020): Conducting Impact and Evaluation Study of the Central Sector Schemes being implemented by Ministry Of Minority Affairs, Government Of India, For the Scheme “National Minorities Development & Finance Corporation (NMDFC)”, Management Development Institute (MDI).
- Patil V B, Deepali M. Gala & Kirti R. Kadam (2002): Effectiveness Of Government Schemes: A Critical Review Of Most Widely Used Schemes, Journal of Xi’an Shiyou University, Natural Science Edition, Vol. 18 (1), pp 430-439
- Elizabeth J., Candida G. Brush, Nancy M., Patricia G. and Myra M. (2009) Diana: A Symbol of Women Entrepreneurs’ Hunt for Knowledge, Money and the Rewards of Entrepreneurship, Springer Small Business Economics February, Vol. 32 (2), pp 129–144
- D. Moorthy and Christina Jeyadevi (2023): A Study on Awareness of Central Government Schemes for the Sustainable Development of Rural India with Reference to Coimbatore International Journal of Engineering and Management Research Vol. 13 (3)
- P. Srinivasa Rao (2019): Rural Development Schemes in India – A Study, 1 International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR) Vol. 06 (1), pp 1072-1076
- Farooq Ahmad Ganjee (2014), ‘Transforming Rural India (2018-19), Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India’, International Journal of English Language, Literature and Humanities, Vol. 1 (5)